

ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY FOR RADIO FREQUENCY EFFECTS (RFE)

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Abstract

We have expanded the concept of radio frequency interference (RFI) to include RF damage and propose that it be termed radio frequency effects (RFE). We have developed a methodology which is an adaptation of the methodology used for electromagnetic pulse (EMP) assessments. The basic parameters in this methodology are RF coupling, transmission loss, and threshold of component effect. When these parameters are represented by their probability distributions, they can be combined to estimate the probability of system failure very simply and accurately.

Introduction

The trend in technology towards higher power radio frequency (RF) sources, more sensitive receivers and sensors, and very-large-scale integrated circuits (VLSI) causes systems to be more easily upset and damaged by RF energy.

It is well known that RF energy can cause adverse effects in electronic systems. Typically the effect is one of creating extraneous signals that interfere with the normal system operation. If the RF energy transferred to the electronics is high enough, the potential exists for long-term upset or latchup (upset lasting longer than the RF transient) and/or permanent damage. We consider both interference and damage in the topic of RF effects (RFE).

Those who have been working in the field of RFI for many years can, by inspection, quickly determine where a system's problem areas will be, how severe they will be, and what needs to be done to reduce them. The present way to teach those not experienced in RFI is to familiarize them with the huge collection of data on the subject. The RFI assessment community needs a simple methodology allowing for easier teaching and permitting more detailed analysis of the elements of the methodology.

The electromagnetic pulse (EMP) assessment methodology considers coupling of energy to the system, interaction of the energy with the system components, circuit modeling of the responses, and the results of component upset and/or damage. The issues of coupling and component damage or upset are applicable to the RFE problem, but EMP interaction and circuit modeling are not relevant at high frequencies where components cannot be accurately represented by equivalent circuits. For example, the inductance of the leads on components may have negligible effect for EMP frequencies, but for RF the inductance of the leads can dominate the response of the component.

We have developed an assessment methodology to predict the RF power density incident on a system that would cause upset or damage to the system electronics. This RFE assessment methodology is based on the EMP assessment methodology, but modified for the microwave frequency regime (1 to 100 GHz). The general assessment methodology for a system with a single entry path and critical component is

shown in figure 1. First, the system under investigation is surveyed to identify the critical components and candidate RF entry ports. Next, these areas are characterized in detail. Finally, the external power density, S , that defines the susceptibility threshold of the system is determined. The methodology presents the results as a probability of system upset or damage as a function of incident RF power density.

This paper addresses the simple case of a system with a single entry path and a single critical component causing system failure. An example of such a system is an RF receiver where the failure of an amplifier or mixer in the front end can cause system failure. In a typical system, several components and entry paths will be critical. In such cases, if the interactions are independent, the probabilities of failure for all entry paths/components are combined (along with weighting values according to the criticality of each component with respect to the system performance) to generate the total probability of system failure. The methodology presented below provides the basic technique for generating the system probability of failure.

The basic elements of the methodology are shown in figure 2. They include identification and characterization of the RF ports of entry (POE's), the transmission or "feedthrough" loss of the entry path(s) from the POE to the affected component, and the upset or damage effect threshold of the critical component. Each of these parameters can be represented by its bounds for a simple worst-case analysis (maximum coupling and minimum effect threshold) or by its probability distributions for a statistical determination of the system effect threshold. Both cases will be discussed to demonstrate a relatively simple and accurate method of estimating the system effects threshold.

Figure 1. Flow chart of RFE assessment methodology.

Figure 2. Typical RF entry path and critical elements of RFE methodology.

Overview

Basically, a system may be considered susceptible to RF if the power received at an internal mission-critical component, P_r , exceeds the upset or failure level of the component, P_f . The power received at the component may be related to the incident power density on the system by the system's effective RF coupling cross-sectional area, σ , by

$$P_r (W) = S (W/cm^2) \times \sigma (cm^2) \quad (1)$$

By replacing P_r with P_f in equation (1) and solving for the power density, one can determine the incident external power density required for system failure, S_f , for a system that is critically dependent upon that component (i.e., the system susceptibility threshold):

$$S_f (W/cm^2) = P_f / \sigma \quad (2)$$

The coupling cross section, σ , may be further divided into (1) the effective capture area of the POE, A_e , and (2) the transmission loss, L , of the path from the POE to the component, and is given by

$$\sigma = A_e L \quad (3)$$

where L is the loss expressed as a ratio less than one. Substituting equation (3) in equation (2), we have the final form of the expression for the system susceptibility threshold:

$$S_f = P_f / (A_e L) \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is the basic expression used to predict the RF power density required to cause system failure for a system dependent upon a single critical component.

The major problem in determining the susceptibility threshold of a system to RF energy is that the effective POE area, A_e , transmission loss, L , and effect threshold, P_f , of a component are a function of a large number of highly variable factors. The component effect threshold is a function of RF pulse width, τ , risetime, t_r , repetition rate, and carrier frequency, f . The effective area of the POE is dependent on the frequency, polarization, p , and azimuthal and elevation angles of arrival, θ , ϕ , of the RF energy. The transmission loss of the RF entry path is strongly dependent on the RF frequency as well as the number and type of devices between the POE and component. Most of these factors are neither well controlled nor repeatable, but are relatively predictable when carefully analyzed statistically. As a result, the system susceptibility threshold is also somewhat random in nature and ideally should be treated as a probability of system failure rather than a fixed value.

Because of the random variables, the RF susceptibility level of a system cannot be known with certainty. Two basic methods are useful to estimate the susceptibility of a system. The first method is to determine the minimum failure threshold of the critical component and the maximum RF energy coupling and perform a deterministic "worst-case" estimate based on equation (4). The second method is to treat the coupling and failure threshold as random variables and determine the probability of system failure as a function of RF power density. The first method can be useful in determining the minimum RF power density required for system failure, or "worst-case susceptibility level," using the minimum component failure threshold and the maximum energy coupling. The result of the first method is useful as a first-order screening of the severity of the problem, but does not serve as a complete assessment since compounded worst-case values are highly unlikely.

The other approach, the statistical approach, assumes that a statistically significant number of samples have been

measured to describe a probability distribution of failure threshold for components and a probability distribution of the system's effective cross-sectional area. These distributions can be combined for a given RF frequency, pulsewidth, etc, and generate a probability of system failure as a function of the incident RF radiation power density.

When statistical methods are used to represent parameters that were previously considered to be too variable, such as POE coupling area, path loss, and component failure level, it is observed that the parameters are well behaved, and that convenient and effective susceptibility assessments of systems can be made.

RF Port of Entry Coupling (Effective Capture Area)

The effective capture area of antennas for in-band RF frequencies can be determined by radiation patterns normally measured during system development. RF coupling to POE's and antennas above band has been found statistically to be well behaved [1]. For example, figure 3 shows the radiation pattern of a VHF antenna as a function of aspect angle when illuminated with 10-GHz (X-band) RF energy. It is noteworthy that the average gain is not significantly below isotropic. The gain for this antenna is even higher than isotropic at some aspect angles. For most antenna radiation patterns measured out of band, the gain pattern has no prominent lobes, has random nulls, and changes rapidly with small changes in the RF frequency or antenna dimensions. The statistical representation of the gain (i.e., the cumulative distribution function (CDF)) gives the probability that the gain will be less than or equal to a given value for any random angle of RF radiation [2]. The CDF clearly shows that the gain when represented by its probability distribution does not change much even with change of RF frequency and antenna dimensions.

The statistical representation of the gain for a single cut pattern is obtained by placing circles of progressively smaller radius on figure 3. For example, when the circles are 1 dB apart in radius, the CDF of the pattern is derived by measuring the cumulative angle of the pattern that is outside the radius compared to the full 360°. For example, in figure 3 the radiation pattern is outside the +8 dBi radius for a cumulative angle of 2° (2/360 = 5.6 percent of the pattern). This CDF is plotted in figure 4 which show that the gain exceeds +8 dBi 5.6 per-

Figure 3. Radiation pattern of VHF antenna at X-band.

Figure 4. The cumulative distribution function for VHF antenna radiation patterns measured above band for random aspect angle. The dashed line is the CDF for figure 3.

cent of the time for any random angle of illumination. As the circles are made smaller and smaller, the pattern will eventually become larger than the circle, and there is a 100-percent probability that the antenna pattern will be outside the circle.

When the pattern is measured in this way for different frequencies and slight changes in mechanical parameters (which tend to change the pattern), the CDF plots as in figure 4 do not change significantly. Furthermore, since a priori the incident angle of the RF is unknown, the CDF gives the most significant parameter, i.e., the probability that the POE gain relative to isotropic exceeds a given value for a random aspect angle.

Given gain, G , relative to isotropic, the effective POE capture area, A_e , is readily calculated using

$$A_e = G\lambda^2/(4\pi), \quad (5)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the RF. When the gain is 10 dB above isotropic, then the effective area is 10 times larger than that calculated in equation (5).

The CDF as described above is appropriate for a single cut of the antenna pattern, but a radiation pattern is three-dimensional (3-D). In order to avoid possible distortion of the statistics, several cuts of the radiation pattern are taken, and these are analyzed from a solid-angle point of view instead of a single-cut point of view. The solid-angle radiation pattern is derived by using smoothing algorithms that take the measured cuts as sampled points and reconstruct the smooth waveforms for different angles of radiation cuts. The CDF of the 3-D pattern is similar to the single cuts, but it was derived using decreasing spheres of equal gain (actually hemispheres, since the antenna is usually mounted on a ground plane) rather than circles to determine the percentage of the pattern lying outside the sphere. (For antennas not mounted on a ground plane, 4π steradians should be used since the antenna can be illuminated from any angle.) These smoothing algorithms and the need for them are good topics for future research.

A number of antennas have been measured for their above band frequency responses [1]; it has been found that

they tend to be fairly well impedance matched when driven from the antenna port, and their gain profiles tend to look very much alike, giving a median gain around -5 dBi. When resistive matching elements are built into the antenna structure, the median gain can be significantly below -5 dBi.

This statistical description of RF coupling to antennas takes on additional significance when we consider the coupling of RF energy to an unshielded wire over a ground plane. Most RF POE's on a system can be reduced to either an antenna or a wire/cable over a ground plane. When a wire passes through a cavity where the cavity is excited by RF energy, the coupling gets very complicated. Too much effort has been spent on analyzing geometrically simple cavity configurations, not because they represent any configuration that is likely to be encountered, but only because they can be analyzed. A resonant cavity can cause the current on a wire to be higher than it would be if it were exposed to the free-space radiation. The resonances of the cavity are very narrow in frequency and therefore unlikely. Furthermore, any small change in mechanical dimensions will change the cavity's resonant frequencies. When the RF coupling to the cavity is analyzed statistically with frequency as the dominant random variable, the gain/effective area of the enclosed wire is determined more by its geometric optical shielding than by the unique parameters that determine the cavity resonance.

In the same way that many antennas are impedance matched at higher RF frequencies, the wire over a ground plane tends to be matched at its effective feed point. In the same way that some antennas above band are good radiators, so is the wire over a ground plane a good radiator. The CDF for the RF coupling to a wire over a ground plane is still being analyzed, but preliminary indications are that it behaves similarly to antenna coupling out of band.

The preliminary conclusion for this topic is that front-door and back-door RF entry paths of systems (such as antennas and wires over a ground plane respectively) are fairly well described by their CDF's. Further research is needed to test this hypothesis and refine it. Further research is also needed for the effects of cable bundling and shielding. Coupling is a moderately well-controlled element of the new RFE assessment methodology.

Transmission Loss of RF Entry Path

Transmission path or "feedthrough" loss of the RF entry path is easily measured with a network analyzer over the entire RF frequency range and is usually well behaved when the frequencies are within the operating band of the transmission-line elements encountered in the path. When RF is out of band and/or non-transmission-line elements are encountered in the path (e.g., lumped element components, switches, etc) a statistical representation of the loss is useful because it is well behaved and tends to smooth out the high degree of variability.

There may be some concern because the feedthrough loss has been measured on a 50-ohm network analyzer, and the feed line and component are not typically well-controlled 50-ohm devices when exposed to RF energy out of band. This issue has been previously addressed [3] and it was found that these mismatches introduce only about a 2-dB loss with a small uncertainty for lossy transmission lines.

The measured RF loss of a wire bundle is shown in figure 5. The CDF for the loss shown in figure 6 is derived by drawing constant insertion loss lines on figure 5 at successively lower loss levels. The percentage of the frequencies corre-

Figure 5. Feedthrough loss of a typical wire from connector to component in an electronic box.

Figure 6. Cumulative distribution function for transmission loss of entry path for random frequency for figure 5.

sponding to the feedthrough loss that lies above a selected loss line, divided by the total number of frequencies, is the probability that the loss will exceed a given value for any random frequency. This procedure was used for deriving the CDF of the transmission loss shown in figure 6.

Another more convenient method of generating the CDF is as follows. If 100 vertical lines are drawn on figure 5 evenly spaced and covering the entire frequency range, and then the loss at each frequency is listed, the curve can be derived by arranging the 100 loss numbers in order of loss. The first number is 1 percent, the second 2 percent, etc.

The CDF for the transmission loss is more useful in a susceptibility assessment than rapidly changing high values of attenuation. Slight variations in RF frequency and/or mechanical dimensions from system to system can change all the attenuations measured, whereas the statistical representation tends to remain unchanged. When making an assessment, one does not know what the exact frequency of the interference will be; therefore, the CDF of the loss is more useful and relevant.

Some issues need to be addressed in making the "feedthrough loss" measurements more significant. For example, care must be exercised to define each end of the network being measured. A special connector may have to be made to have a well-defined feed point without unnecessary interfering ground path inductance. The receive point must also be carefully designed in that the component should be removed and miniature coax installed at the input to the component. This coaxial cable should be embedded in the nearest

ground plane to prevent coupling via the outer conductor of the cable and also to reduce ground path inductance.

It may be that general rules can be derived for boxes that give the distribution of losses as a function of volume or internal Q . What is needed is a hierarchy of successively more accurate information for making assessments, based on how many measurements can be made on systems being assessed. A factor in deciding to spend time and money making additional measurements is whether the reduction of uncertainty is significant. In the statistical realm, only the largest uncertainties are worth reducing.

Component Effect Threshold

The typical effect on a component of exposure to RF energy is upset or damage. Rectification of interfering RF by a semiconductor junction causes a bias shift during the interfering pulse (and possibly after it), which can cause a false indication of some voltage threshold device, can contribute to upset in a digital circuit if it occurs at the right time of the digital clock pulse, or, if the interfering pulse is periodic and falls within the pass band of some sensing circuit, can give a false signal. In some cases the interfering signal can be so strong that it exceeds the damage threshold of the semiconductor junction.

The conventional approach to characterizing the RF effect threshold of semiconductors is to measure their upset or damage thresholds in terms of absorbed power [3]. Figure 7 is the measured RF rectification sensitivity of some integrated circuits. Richardson [3] has proposed that the absorbed power level that gives 100 mV be used as a standard for characterizing the efficiency of a specific junction in converting RF energy to DC. The detected voltage for incident power rises rapidly as the RF power is increased, giving the 100 mV observed by Richardson, making the 100-mV level even more significant. The difference between incident and absorbed power at that level is not significant. Note that the devices tend to give this response around the 1- to 2-mW incident RF power level.

Different types and levels of integrated circuit technology (both processing and scaling) have been damage tested with single 0.1- μ s RF pulses at S- and X-bands, as shown in figure 8. The few RF damage measurements that have been made

Figure 7. RF rectification properties of integrated circuits: absorbed RF power required for 100 mV bias shift.

Figure 8. Damage thresholds of integrated circuits at 3 and 10 GHz for RF pulses of 0.1 µs.

on integrated circuits have given a rather narrow distribution. The limited data that are available (2 to 6 devices each) fall within the ranges shown in the figure.

Probability of System Failure

The probability of RF-induced system failure (upset or damage) may be estimated by combining the probability distributions for each element of the methodology as discussed. The important factor in the utility of the methodology is the use of the probability distribution functions for each of the parameters. If each of the distributions discussed are Gaussian in the decibel domain (lognormal distribution), then they combine in a simple way to give the overall probability of system failure. If the distributions of the POE effective area, transmission path loss, and component failure threshold when plotted on graph paper are all straight lines, then the distributions are Gaussian. Moreover, if the distributions are both Gaussian and independent, the means of the distribution for the effective area, path loss, and component failure threshold can be added to form the mean RF power density for system failure. The individual standard deviations can be combined as the root of the sum of the squares to form the standard deviation of the system failure level. The total probability of failure curve (CDF) allows the probability of system failure (or the complement probability of survival) to be easily read directly from the curve as a function of incident RF power density.

The amount of distortion due to not having perfect Gaussian distributions is compared in figure 9, in which the means and standard deviations of each of the individual distributions are combined and compared to all combinations of a sample of the CDF's for effective area, loss, and component effect threshold. The differences tend to be mainly in the outer ends of the distributions beyond approximately plus or minus two times the standard deviation. An important facet of combining the distributions is that the smaller deviations tend to be obscured by the larger ones, in effect justifying refinement only of the larger uncertainties.

The probability of failure curve shown in figure 9 is an example probability of failure (upset) curve for a hypothetical system for the antenna radiation statistics of figure 4, the feedthrough loss statistics of figure 6, and a component upset (failure) value of 1 to 2 mW, taken from figure 7. This set of parameters was selected because the RF coupling to a wire over a ground plane is typical of many system configurations and the antenna distribution shown in figure 4 is considered to be like that of a wire over a ground plane. The feedthrough loss of figure 6 is typical of what could be encountered in a system and further had some curvature indicating that it is

Figure 9. Probability of system upset versus RF power density based on RF coupling to a wire over a ground plane as typically represented by figure 3, feedthrough loss of figure 5, and an upsetting threshold of 1 to 2 mW from figure 7.

non-Gaussian. The upset level of about 1 to 2 mW (from figure 7) would give around 100 mV, which might be troublesome in many systems.

The CDF curves for effective area and loss (figures 4 and 6) were estimated to be Gaussian for a line drawn between the 25-percent point on the data and the 75-percent point. This gave half the data above the line and half below it. The actual data from the curves were combined by adding samples in all possible combinations to give the data points shown in figure 9. The average RF power density required to cause upset is -3.0 ± 11.1 dBWi. * This is to be compared to -2.4 ± 10.8 dBWi, the value calculated by assuming individual Gaussian distributions for each of the elements and simply combining the means and standard deviations of the individual probability distributions. The result is very good agreement. The deviation from a straight line was observed only at the ends of the distribution. More experience is needed in interpreting these parameters for different conditions to make more reliable observations about the shortcuts that can be taken.

Conclusions

This assessment methodology allows an analyst to make a simple worst-case estimate of the failure threshold of a system, or, with a little more data, an estimate of the probability of system failure (including upset) as a function of the incident RF power density, by combining the bounds or probability distributions of the POE effect area, entry path transmission loss, and component failure threshold.

For the POE gain/effective area, it has been found that both the RF coupling to the antenna out of band and wire over a ground plane tend to show similar random multilobed patterns that, when represented by their CDF's, show an average gain of -5 dBi. There is an opportunity for further refinement in

*The term dBWi is a unit derived from combining the POE area, loss, and component effect threshold CDF's. The term dBW indicates power relative to 1 W, and i refers to the gain of an isotropic radiator. The -3.0 dBWi can be translated to RF power density by taking a specific radio frequency and calculating the isotropic effective capture area of the POE using equation (5). For example, the isotropic effective capture area at 3 GHz is 8 cm^2 and -3 dBW is equivalent to 0.5 W ; therefore the power density is $0.5 \text{ W}/8.0 \text{ cm}^2 = 63 \text{ mW/cm}^2$, which corresponds to 500 V/m RMS .

the area of interpolating the 3-D antenna patterns from antenna cuts.

For the entry path transmission loss, again the high variability of the RF loss as a function of frequency and system design tends to indicate that a CDF is very useful in system assessments. The issue that needs to be addressed is the measurement of the interface impedances to allow development of equivalent circuits for modeling of systems and quality control tests of the damage and upset thresholds for components.

For the component effect threshold characterization, very limited data on RF testing of a few devices has given relatively narrow probability distributions, but indicates that the uncertainty is not as large as the RF coupling uncertainty. Should further investigation prove this to be true, then it may be more efficient to study the coupling uncertainties, since these would tend to dominate.

The difference in determining the actual probability of system failure by combining the individual distributions in every possible way may be small compared to the estimated mean and standard deviation calculated by assuming independent, Gaussian distributions if the individual distributions are reasonably close to a normal distribution. This allows a much simpler method for calculating the average RF power density for system failure than performing the detailed convolutions of the distributions.

By allowing us to focus on each element of the new methodology, the methodology lets us improve the assess-

ments we can make with minimal information. We can look at configurations and immediately spot problem areas, and we can assess systems quite accurately.

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